

A simple method for assessing core reactivity during load-following transients

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a method for determining core reactivity during reactor state changes. The method is based on the interpretation of the spatio-temporal evolution of the neutron flux with the two-group diffusion kinetics equations. Differently from other methods this one does not rely on the inverse kinetics equations but is based on the comparison between the steady state and kinetics diffusion equation. A physical interpretation of the different terms composing the reactivity is provided, as well as an example on a ramp during a load-following transient.

Keywords: Reactivity monitoring, Inverse kinetics, Transient analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

The determination of the core reactivity is one of the functions provided by core monitoring systems. Methods devoted to this purpose, based on the neutron kinetics equations, have been proposed for several decades and most of them are used in the reactivity meters. In the early days of nuclear development, Murray et al. [1] wrote the one-group point kinetics equations in terms of reduced variables: the ratios of the neutron and precursors densities over their equilibrium values. The equation related to the reduced neutron density was solved in terms of the reactivity, providing in this way the time-dependent reactivity as a function of the desired neutron density variation. Several reduced neutron density functions were proposed, such as a step or a ramp function. This method was improved by Ferguson et al. [2], who applied the space-time factorized form of the flux, introduced by Henry (1958) [3], to compute the amplitude function as the ratio between the convolutions of the flux and shape function onto the adjoint flux. Since in reality the flux, and adjoint flux are not available, detectors readings and precomputed weighting functions were used instead. The amplitude function was then inserted into Murray's formula to determine the reactivity. When using a more detailed approach based on the space-dependent neutron density, a weight function is needed. One crucial requirement of this function is to be independent of the shape of the neutron density inside the core, in order to avoid the lack of proportionality between the amplitude function and the detector readings during the transient. To achieve this goal, Christoskov and Petkov [4] proposed a procedure for the computation of bilinear weighted core kinetics parameters. An inverse kinetics method was then used for the experimental reactivity determination. Another inverse method was proposed by Suescún-Díaz et al. [5] with a second order point reactor kinetics model based on the P1 approximation of the transport theory. The particularity of the P1 point reactor model is to implicitly consider the time derivative of the neutron source. Another inverse point kinetics method was proposed by Gadomski et al. [6] using some approximations such as taking the neutron density as the average inside small time intervals, computing the time derivative assuming a linear evolution inside the interval and using the coefficients of the straight line to integrate

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the precursors equation. A numerical estimation of the accuracy of the method was done. The approach presented here is based on the comparison of the kinetics and steady state neutronics equations, which yields an expression of the reactivity composed of two terms. A physical interpretation of these terms is provided and an example on power ramps is given. Due to the assumptions made, the formulation can only be applied to slow transients, such as those that occur during normal reactor operation.

2. DEDUCTION OF THE REACTIVITY FROM THE KINETIC EQUATIONS

The neutron kinetics equation in two energy groups, using standard notations, can be written as follows:

$$\frac{dn}{dt} = A \cdot \Phi + \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \sum_{i=1}^6 \lambda_i C_i, \quad (1)$$

where:

- n is the neutron density vector:

$$n = \begin{pmatrix} n_1 \\ n_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

- A is the operator:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} [(1 - \beta)\nu\Sigma_{f1} - \Sigma_{a1} - \Sigma_r - D_1B^2 - \nabla \cdot D_1\nabla] & (1 - \beta)\nu\Sigma_{f2} \\ \Sigma_r & [-\Sigma_{a2} - D_2B^2 - \nabla \cdot D_2\nabla] \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

- C_i and λ_i are the concentrations of delayed neutron precursor nuclides and their decay constants, respectively,
- β is the sum of the delayed fractions beta β_i of the fission emitted neutrons,
- B^2 is the transverse buckling, which takes into account radial or axial leakage in case of 1D or 2D model,
- Φ is the flux vector:

$$\Phi = \begin{pmatrix} \Phi_1 \\ \Phi_2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

We assume that the reactor is homogeneous, therefore the cross sections appearing in Eq. (3) do not depend on space. Calling v_1 and v_2 the velocities of the fast and thermal fluxes, and defining the matrix operator:

$$V^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/v_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/v_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

we can write the relationship between neutron density and neutron flux as:

$$n = V^{-1} \cdot \Phi \quad (6)$$

and Eq. (1) becomes:

$$\frac{d}{dt} (V^{-1} \cdot \Phi) = A \cdot \Phi + \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \sum_{i=1}^6 \lambda_i C_i. \quad (7)$$

Let us now introduce the operator A_k , which describes the reactor as if it were critical with the eigenvalue k . The related neutron flux Φ_k satisfies the relation:

$$A_k \cdot \Phi_k = 0. \quad (8)$$

Operator A_k differs from A for the presence of $1/k$ instead of $(1 - \beta)$ as presented below:

$$A = A_k + \left(1 - \beta - \frac{1}{k}\right) F \cdot \Phi, \quad (9)$$

where operator F is:

$$F = \begin{pmatrix} \nu \Sigma_{f1} & \nu \Sigma_{f2} \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

Inserting Eq. (9) inside Eq. (7) we obtain:

$$\frac{d}{dt} V^{-1} \cdot \Phi = A_k \cdot \Phi + \left(1 - \beta - \frac{1}{k}\right) F \cdot \Phi + \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \sum_{i=1}^6 \lambda_i C_i. \quad (11)$$

As is commonly done in first-order perturbation theory, let us call Φ_k^* the importance of the neutrons, which is the solution of the problem adjoint to Eq. (8).

Taking into account that by definition of adjoint operator we have $\langle \Phi_k^*, A_k \cdot \Phi \rangle = \langle \Phi_k^* \cdot A_k, \Phi \rangle = 0$, the convolution of the Eq. (11) onto Φ_k^* gives:

$$\left\langle \Phi_k^*, \frac{d}{dt} (V^{-1} \cdot \Phi) \right\rangle = \left(1 - \beta - \frac{1}{k}\right) \langle \Phi_{k,1}^*, F \cdot \Phi \rangle + \sum_{i=1}^6 \lambda_i \langle \Phi_{k,1}^*, C_i \rangle. \quad (12)$$

where the notation $\Phi_{k,1}^*$ refers to the fast component of the adjoint flux, since it was assumed that only fast neutrons were emitted by fission. With the following notations:

$$P = \left\langle \Phi_k^*, \frac{d}{dt} (V^{-1} \cdot \Phi) \right\rangle, \quad N = \langle \Phi_{k,1}^*, F \cdot \Phi \rangle, \quad D = \sum_{i=1}^6 \lambda_i \langle \Phi_{k,1}^*, C_i \rangle, \quad (13)$$

we can write Eq. (12) as

$$P = \left(1 - \beta - \frac{1}{k}\right) N + D. \quad (14)$$

Note that within the term P , the convolution applies to both space and energy, while within the terms N and D , it applies only to space.

The reactivity $\rho = 1 - 1/k$ can be obtained solving Eq. (14), which gives:

$$\rho = \frac{P}{N} - \left(\frac{D}{N} - \beta\right). \quad (15)$$

We can distinguish two terms that contribute to the definition of reactivity at time t :

- the first term is the ratio between the rate of change of the neutron density (weighted by the importance) and the neutron birth rate (also weighted by the importance),
- the second term is the excess of the delayed fraction D/N of the born neutrons (weighted by the importance of these neutrons) with respect to the equilibrium value β .

For the determination of the term D we need the concentrations C_i of the precursor nuclides. They satisfy the relationship:

$$\frac{dC_i}{dt} = \beta_i \left(\nu \Sigma_{f,1} \Phi_1 + \nu \Sigma_{f,2} \Phi_2 \right) - \lambda_i C_i, \quad (16)$$

whose solution is:

$$C_i(t) = C_{i,0} e^{-\lambda_i t} + \beta_i \int_0^t \left(\nu \Sigma_{f,1} \Phi_1(\tau) + \nu \Sigma_{f,2} \Phi_2(\tau) \right) e^{-\lambda_i(t-\tau)} d\tau, \quad (17)$$

with the initial concentrations $C_{i,0}$ given by:

$$C_{i,0} = \frac{\beta_i}{\lambda_i} \left(\nu \Sigma_{f1} \Phi_1(0) + \nu \Sigma_{f2} \Phi_2(0) \right). \quad (18)$$

Inserting Eq. (17) into Eq. (13) we obtain the term D during the transient :

$$D = \sum_{i=1}^6 \beta_i e^{-\lambda_i t} \left(N(0) + \lambda_i \int_0^t \left\langle \Phi_{k,1}^*, \left(\nu \Sigma_{f,1} \Phi_1(\tau) + \nu \Sigma_{f,2} \Phi_2(\tau) \right) \right\rangle e^{-\lambda_i \tau} d\tau \right), \quad (19)$$

which enables computing the reactivity with Eq. (15).

3. SIMPLIFICATIONS

In the prototype version the approach described in section 2 to evaluate the reactivity has been implemented with some approximations which are presented below.

3.1. Calculation of fluxes

The fluxes Φ_1 and Φ_2 that appear in the integrals used to calculate the reactivity are those that satisfy the kinetic problem defined in Eq. (1). The problem can be simplified by replacing these fluxes with those that satisfy the steady state problem defined by Eq. (8). Indeed, the difference between these fluxes is not significant if the transient being processed is sufficiently slow. Moreover, we assume that to get from the state at time t to the state at time $t + \Delta t$, the product $\nu\Sigma_{f,g}\Phi_g$ vary linearly.

3.2. Calculation of the adjoint flux

Inside the core, at a sufficient distance from the reflector, the spatial form of the adjoint flux differs slightly from that of the fast forward flux Φ_1 and the fast to thermal ratio is assumed as constant. In other words we make the following approximation:

$$\Phi_k^* = \begin{pmatrix} s \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \Phi_1, \quad (20)$$

where s is the average adjoint spectrum. Inserting Eq. (20) into the equation adjoint to Eq. (8) and solving with respect s we obtain:

$$s = \frac{\langle \nu\Sigma_{f,2}\Phi_1 \rangle}{k \langle (\Sigma_{a,2} + D_2B^2 + \nabla \cdot D_2\nabla) \Phi_1 \rangle}. \quad (21)$$

This relationship is only valid for two-group theory.

4. EVALUATION WITH A 1D MODEL

Two types of calculations were performed with a two-energy-group one-dimensional model to test the various simplifications:

- a. Programming the simplification described in Section 3.1
- b. Programming the simplifications described in Sections 3.1 and 3.2.

The results are shown in Table I.

Table I. Reactivity during a load-follow ramp.

Power ramp (%/min)	Time (min)	ρ_a (pcm)	ρ_b (pcm)
	0	0	0
-1.67	3	-2	-2
	6	-2	-2
	0	0	0
-4.17	1.2	-5.5	-5.4
	2.4	-6.5	-6.3

5. CONCLUSIONS

The method proposed is at a prototype level. Given the assumptions made, the formulation can only be applied to slow transients, such as those that occur during normal reactor operation. Fast transients, such as the control rod ejection, are outside its range of validity. A further study would be desirable to assess the impact of the approximations on the reactivity value. This could be done by studying homogeneous core configurations with a more accurate model and comparing them with classical kinetic solutions. Furthermore, a comparison with kinetic codes could be made. Such comparisons could be useful in determining the validity limits of this study (for example, up to what power ramp can good results be achieved). Knowing such applicability limits could allow the definition of an on-site calibration procedure for the reactivity meter if the algorithm described above could be integrated into the core monitoring system.

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